

Stability of Prometabolite – Cell free supernatant (CFS) of *Pediococcus acidilactici*, *Pediococcus lolii* and commercial probiotic

Stability of Prometabolite

- Pepsin treatment (1mg/mL - 6 hours incubation)
- Pancreatin treatment (3mg/mL - 6 hours incubation)

Protein Precipitation– Cell free supernatant (CFS) of *Pediococcus acidilactici* and *Pediococcus lolii*, *Pediococcus lolii* and commercial probiotic

Protein Precipitation Experiment

- Ammonium sulfate precipitation
- Methanol precipitation
- Trichloroacetic acid precipitation of peptides and proteins

Size exclusion spin coloum chromatography <3Kda Peptide

Size Exclusion Chromatography

- Probiotic cell free supernatant were collected after 24h of incubation at 37°C based on centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 20 min
- <3Kda spin column applied to separated low molecular weight thermostable proteins

Antibacterial activity was absent after the precipitation of proteins in the sample

